

Guidelines on research data management for Spoke6_MOST

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Form for dataset description

Version

Date	Version	Author	Description	Status
08/04/2024	V0	Andrea Solieri	First Draft	Draft
10/04/2024	V1.0	Andrea Solieri	Draft after collection of inputs by colleagues	Draft
11/04/2024	V1.1	Andrea Solieri	Finalised version	Final draft

Guidelines on research data management

Guidelines on how to manage data during the project as to make it FAIR and ready for sharing once the project is finished.

DATA ORGANISATION		
ISSUE	ACTIONS	NOTES
Folders organisation	Set up a clear directory structure that includes information like the project title, a date, and some type of unique identifier. Consider the best hierarchy for files, deciding whether a deep or shallow hierarchy is preferable.	Directory structure examples <i>When working in collaboration with others, the need for an orderly structure is high.</i>
File naming	Be consistent and descriptive in naming and organising files. Choose a format for naming your files and use it consistently. Include in the directory a readme.txt file that explains your naming format along with any abbreviations or codes you have used.	Naming conventions <i>How you organise and name your files will have a big impact on your ability to find those files later and to understand what they contain.</i>
Version control	Decide how many versions of a file to keep, which versions to keep, for how long and how to organise versions When creating new versions of your files, record what changes are being made to the files and give the new files a unique name.	Semantic versioning spec <i>Versioning refers to saving new copies of your files when you make changes so that you can go back and retrieve specific versions of your files later.</i>
File formats	Save data in a non-proprietary (open) and standard file format when possible. When it is necessary to save files in a proprietary format, consider including a readme.txt file in your directory that documents the name and version of the software used to generate the file	Recommended Formats <i>The file formats you use have a direct impact on your ability to open those files at a later date and on the ability of other people to access those data.</i>
Quality control	Ensure that the data recorded reflect the actual facts, responses, observations and events. Document in detail how data is collected.	Quality control actions <i>Quality control of data is an integral part of all research and takes place at various stages, during data collection, data entry</i>

		<i>or digitisation, and data checking.</i>
DATA DESCRIPTION		
ISSUE	ACTIONS	NOTES
Vocabularies	<p>Use both foundation ontologies and domain specific taxonomies.</p> <p>Use common vocabularies related to air, waterborne, rail, urban and light mobility the documents in order to share information with the mobility communities. Add descriptive information and semantic annotations.</p>	<p>Foundation ontologies Domain specific taxonomies IEEE standards SAE standards Metadata Standards Catalog Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV)</p> <p><i>Foundation ontologies cover the basic ontologies used across different domains. By combining a core ontology with domain-specific taxonomies, you can create a flexible and well-structured knowledge base for your data.</i></p>
Documentation	<p>Document data appropriately. Explain the procedures and fieldwork methods, the objectives and methodology of the research. Describe the meanings of variables and codes used. Describe any derivation, transformations, de-identification (pseudonymisation and or anonymisation) or data cleaning carried out. Give information for citing and discovering data. Always attach a readme file.</p>	<p>Guidelines for creating a README file</p> <p>Summary of a range of documentation methods for research data</p>
DATA SECURITY		
ISSUE	ACTIONS	NOTES
Access control	<p>Answer the questions: Who would be able to access your data? What might they be able to do with it? Are any specific use restrictions required? How long do you want the data to be available?</p>	<p><i>Data security arrangements need to be proportionate to the nature of the data and the risks involved.</i></p>
Backup strategy	<p>Make a risk analysis for planning a backup strategy. Define a backup strategy: how often you should back up your data, how many copies you should have (follow the rule 3-2-1), where you store it.</p>	<p><i>3-2-1 rule: you should have at least 3 copies of your data, stored on 2 different types of media, with 1 copy kept off-site.</i></p>

	Where data contains personal information, take care to create only the minimal number of copies needed, for example, a master file and one backup copy, which is encrypted and securely stored.	
Storage of confidential, sensitive and personal data	Personal information can be removed from data files and stored separately under more stringent security measures.	<i>Personal information must be treated with more care than data that do not</i>
Encryption	Individual files can be encrypted, as can folders or entire disk volumes and USB storage devices. Any digital files or folders, which contain sensitive information and data should be encrypted.	VeraCrypt for Windows, Mac OSX and Linux BitLocker for Windows
Anonymization	Find and assess identifiers. Implement anonymisation techniques. Review the data and re-assess any remaining disclosure risk. Carefully consider the applicable legislation as this will influence the definition of anonymised data.	Practical considerations for data anonymisation Amnesia tool for anonymization

Form for dataset description

Link google form:

The following table should be completed for each dataset.

DATA SUMMARY	
Dataset	Title of the dataset
Institution responsible for the dataset	Name of the institution responsible for the data
Institutional partner involved in the dataset generation	Institutional partners involved in the dataset creation (if that is the case)
Industrial partner involved in the dataset generation	Industrial partners involved in the dataset creation (if that is the case)
Related Scenario	Title of the scenarios related the dataset
Purpose of the dataset	Purpose of the dataset and its relations to the objectives of the project
Dataset generation	Did you use primary or/and secondary data in the dataset?
Dataset type	What is the type of data (included in the dataset)?
Dataset format	Please provide the extension of dataset file (e.g. .txt, .xlm, etc.)
Volume of data	Please specify the size of the dataset file (both the number and unit of measurement in MB or GB, e.g. 10 MB; 2 TB, etc.)
FAIR DATA	

Persistent identifier	Please provide the DOI of the dataset
Data repository	What is the data repository? <i>Please note that Zenodo is the preferred choice</i>
Openness	Is the dataset openly available?
Licencing	What is the licence applied to the dataset?
Reason for not sharing	If there are restrictions on sharing, please explain which and why
Restrictions	If there are restrictions on sharing, please explain how access can be provided (e.g. personal request)
Methods, tools and softwares	Please describe methods, tools or softwares required to access the dataset (if any)
Vocabularies	Which vocabulary/ontology/taxonomy have you used?
Vocabularies specs	Please specify the vocabulary/ontology/taxonomy you have used, according to your previous reply (e.g. IEEE standards, SAE standards, etc.)
Search keywords	What are the search keywords to make the dataset findable? <i>Please note that you should always include "CNMS MOST" and "SPOKE 6 Connected and Automated Vehicle (CAV)"</i>
Timing for reuse	When do you plan to make the dataset available for reuse?
Support for reuse	Will you provide any support for data reuse?
LEGAL, ECONOMIC AND ETHICAL ASPECTS	
Legal issues	Are there any legal barriers that can impact the sharing of the dataset (e.g. privacy issues, licence restrictions, etc.)?
Economic issues	Are there any economic issues that can impact the sharing of the dataset?
Ethical issues	Are there any ethical issues that can impact the sharing of the dataset (e.g. personal data)?
Personal and sensitive data	<p>If there is any personal data or sensitive data in the dataset, describe how you dealt with this aspect.</p> <p>Personal data is any piece of information that someone can use to identify, with some degree of accuracy, a living person.</p> <p>Sensitive personal data is a specific set of "special categories" that must be treated with extra security.</p>